

DEFECT ASSESSMENT, UNDER FATIGUE, OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES CONTAINING CRACKS

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ABSTRACT

The use of composite metal/epoxy/adhesive combinations in advanced engineering structures is widely accepted. The presence of cracks and the subsequent growth of them by fatigue could render the structures unsafe. Finite element calculations of a crack present in the metal of a metal/epoxy sandwich layer has shown that the stress intensity factor calibrations can vary depending on the type of constraint modelled. Two representative materials, an aluminium alloy and a low alloy steel, are used in the analysis. A fatigue life sensitivity analysis reveals upper and lower bounds that depend on material geometry and the type of bonding that exists in the adhesive. The defect assessment procedure R6 is applied to compare bounds on tolerable crack sizes for a range of crack profiles.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced high performance materials are an essential part of today's industries. Epoxy/resin and epoxy/substrate composites are widely used in this respect and their failure modes and methods of analysis are consequently of great interest to engineers. It is important that, within the design life of these structures where fatigue loading conditions exist, cracks introduced during fabrication or cracks initiated during operation do not propagate.

There are numerous applications where engineering metals and epoxies are prepared in close contact with each other and where the crack growth mode is determined to be due to fatigue. Crack propagation in the metal or the metal/epoxy contact will effectively mean reduction in the safe life of the component. Methodologies exist to predict failure by fatigue in metal structures alone (1-2). These methods can be extended to composites in purely fracture mechanics terms as long as the stress analysis that is undertaken is relevant to the boundary conditions prevailing in the composite structure. The factors that need to be considered are the loading and boundary conditions, the crack profiles and the failure mode. In many cases upperbound estimates can be made to calculate the crack tip elastic stresses in two dimensions but for a more accurate determination the use of finite element modelling is also available (3-6).

Two metals of widely different strengths, an aluminium alloy and a low alloy steel, are considered in the analysis together with representative material data for an epoxy resin. Elastic

finite element calculations of a crack present in the metal of a metal/epoxy sandwich layer has been performed. Different crack shapes ranging from elliptical cracks with a range of aspect ratios were analysed and their stress intensity factor K values were compared with available calibrations for penny shaped and infinite plate cracks. The metal epoxy composite layer was modelled in two ways. First with shared nodes at the interface producing a rigid interface and a higher load carrying capacity and also with multi-point constraint which allows a sharp drop in stress at the interface. From available fatigue crack growth data a sensitivity study is carried out to predict the number of cycles to failure for a composite metal/epoxy plate described by a range of plates containing crack. The defect assessment procedure R6 is applied in a sensitivity analysis to determine bounds on tolerable crack sizes for a range of crack profiles. The role of the adhesive/epoxy is considered, not in terms of its fatigue strength as it is a third order effect compared to the metal, but in terms of its bonding and the subsequent increase in constraint and life extension in the fatigue life of the metal.

FRACTURE MECHANICS ASSESSMENT

Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) is widely used in the defect assessment of engineering components and structures. Its usefulness is greatly enhanced in practice if the behaviour of three-dimensional, 3D, cracks can be predicted. This type of analysis is not always possible and use is made of simple models involving two dimensional, 2D, idealisations. In plates and shells references [1-8] are available for a number of loading conditions and cracked geometries. A comparison of full 3D, 2D and quasi-2D results for surface cracks in plates has shown the 3D results generally to be lower, emphasising the benefit of a full finite element 3D analysis. However by using the upperbounds for the stress intensity factor K for a particular structure conservative design estimates may be arrived. The stress intensity factor K for any geometry can be expressed in terms of stress and crack size as

$$K = Y \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (1)$$

where the geometry factor Y is available for a number of shapes range of crack lengths and loading conditions (1-9). Generally for thumbnail cracks of various a/c ratios Y ranges from .66 to 1.4 and for an extended crack from 1.12 to values $\gg 1$ depending on crack depth. The present study identifies the bounds for Y and presents an analysis for defect assessment for a composite plate.

The propagation of the crack due to fatigue can then be considered as the next step in the methodology. In this procedure the fatigue process can be simplified to failure stages consisting of steady state fatigue crack growth which is beyond the threshold region, and prior to unstable fast fracture. In components, such as turbine blades, which are not permitted to tolerate any cracks, design of lifing will be based on initiation. But in most composite components, such as in large frames, small crack may exist without compromising safety. In such cases the steady state fatigue crack growth regime in the metal can be considered. The classical equation that describe fatigue crack growth in the elastic regime is the Paris (9) law given as;

$$da/dN = C \Delta K^m \quad (2)$$

where K is the stress intensity factor, a is the crack length, N is the number of fatigue cycles and C and m are material constants. Materials fatigue crack growth data are available (8-13) in a number of engineering materials and epoxies. Numerical analysis is usually required, but assuming constant Y integration gives;

$$N = \left(\frac{2}{(m-2)} \cdot C \cdot Y^m \cdot \Delta \sigma^m \right) \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{a_i^{(m-2/2)}} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{a_f^{(m-2/2)}} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

where a_i is the initial crack length, a_f is the final crack length, N is the number of cycles and σ is the applied stress. The number of cycles to failure can then be determined for various geometries and crack sizes and the analysis can be extended to compare different materials for their relative fatigue strength.

R6 Assessment Procedure

The R6 procedure (1-2) is relevant to describing fracture in brittle and ductile materials. A failure assessment curve is produced in terms of K_r and L_r which are defined as

$$K_r = K/K_{IC} \quad (4)$$

$$L_r = P/P_L \quad (5)$$

where P is the applied load, P_L is the plastic yield load of the flawed structure which derivable from the yield stress of the material, K_{IC} is a material constant describing the critical fracture stress. Values of $K_r = 1$ correspond with brittle fracture and value of $L_r > 1$ represents ductile failure. In applying R6, the yield stress and K_{IC} information for a material is needed. Table 1 shows the representative material properties used in the present analysis.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of representative low alloy steel (13), Aluminium (12) and Epoxy (11)

Material	σ_y , MPa	E, GPa	C	m	K_{IC}
STEEL	1000	220	5 E-13	4.2	110
ALUMINIUM	460	150	4 E-12	4.3	22
EPOXY	2	3	2 E-9	6.1	

The R6 analysis is applied to evaluate the relative crack growth behaviour of the steel and the aluminium using the bounds developed in the Y factors.

Figure 1: Stringer/skin bonded joints consisting of an extruded section stiffener showing possible crack sites.

Figure 2: Model plate section of the composite joint consisting of metal/epoxy/metal bonded joints.

Stress analysis and modelling

Figure 1 shows an example of an extruded section bonded to a plate. The number of extruded section will usually depend on the type of application and the strength required. This a typical structure of a simple composite structure. This model is simplified for modelling to a composite plate under tension. Figure 2 shows the simplified 3D model of the plate containing an elliptical crack in the metal surface of the plate. The ABAQUS finite element package (14) was used for the 3-D analysis. A crack shape ratio of $a/c=0.4$ was chosen and the thickness of the total sandwich was set to be 6 mm making each plate 3mm in size. The thickness of the epoxy was assumed to be minimal. The load is applied in the direction normal to the crack and the adhesive act as a strong bond to constrain the two plates together. This plate has been modelled using finite element elastic computational techniques.

The stress analysis of the bonded frame, with and without the epoxy layer, was performed under a constant displacement loading condition. Two methods of interface conditions were employed to simulate the bonding. In one case the interface was made to be rigid with fixed nodes at the interface increasing the load bearing capacity to the opposite metal plate thus making the structure more rigid. In the second method multi-point constraint (MPC) is imposed at the two sets of nodes at the interface allowing a sharp drop in stress between metal and epoxy. This could simulate a situation where de-bonding has occurred or where bonding yields to prevent full distribution of stresses to the other section of the composite. Added complications of residual stresses that may occur as a result of curing between the metal and epoxy (15) were not modelled for the present purposes. Calculations of the LEFM non-dimensional stress intensity shape factor Y were made for three cases using the elastic J-Contour integral output from program. Figure (3) shows an example of stresses across the crack tip for two crack length. For the short crack length both the metal and the composite is modelled showing the reduced constraint in the former and for the long crack length differences in applying MPC is shown. It is clear that in both cases changes are not more than 10%.

The results were compared to various results for plates in the literature (1-8) and comparisons for Y are shown in figure 4. The Y factors for a thumbnail crack, a crack in an infinite plate and an

Figure 3 : Variation of Y around the crack front for two crack lengths comparing the difference in crack length and nodal point constraints at the composite interface.

Figure 4: Variation of the Y factor for a range of plates and boundary conditions, relevant to Figure 2, containing cracks

Figure 5 : Typical da/dN versus ΔK behaviour for the three representative materials used in the analysis

Figure 6 : Number of cycles to Failure for the aluminium representative material data for a plate thickness of 3mm using a range of Y factors shown in Figure (5).

elliptical crack in a plate, with two thicknesses of 3 and 6 mm are presented together with the FE calculations. The most constrained is the thumbnail crack and the least constrained is the thin section plate, under constant load, with an elliptical crack. The FE and the FE with the MPC model lie within this band. It is clear that for safe conditions and as a first design estimate the upper and lower bounds for Y can be used to calculate fatigue failure times for the present materials.

Fatigue analysis

Figure 5 shows actual best fit data for the secondary regime of fatigue crack growth for the materials shown in Table 1. By using equations 2 and 3 it is possible to compare relative failure cycles for the steel and the aluminium plates having a thickness of 3 mm for the range of Y factors shown in figure 4. The number of cycles to failure were evaluated using an initial crack length a of 0.1 mm to the full thickness of 3 mm of the first plate in the composite (figure 2). Figures 6 and 7 show the failure times for a stress range of 100-400 MPa for the Y calibrations. In both figures the range in Y factors, shown in Figure 4, translate into a factor of 30 in predicting cycles to failure with the aluminium thin plate giving the shortest life. Figure 8 compares the upper and lower bound for the metals as well as the epoxy over the same stress range. The upperbound in the Aluminium overlaps the steel but it is clear that the epoxy is weak enough to be discounted when considering fatigue as it would fail at an early stage. But what is of importance is that the failure in epoxy bonding reduces the constraint, which will increase the Y factor in the composite, hence allowing for a faster fatigue crack growth in the metal.

R6 Assessment

Depending on the type of application for the composite structure and the importance of a through crack the R6 procedure is a relevant method for predicting safe crack growth extension. By applying equations 4 and 5 and using material data available in Table 1 the R6 diagram can be developed. Figures 9 and 10 show the K_r and L_r boundary where failure occurs predominantly by plastic collapse when the K_r values are low and failure is due to sharp brittle fracture if cracking crosses the line for low values of L_r . The applied stress used for the aluminium is 200 Mpa in figure 9 whereas it is 500 MPa for the steel in Figure 10. It is obvious from the figures that for the applied loads the FE calculations for the plate and the calculations for the thumbnail crack are safe whereas the 3mm Plate fail in both instances predominantly by fast fracture.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

It has been found that the stress intensity factor calibrations can vary by as much as 10% depending on the type of constraint modelled and by a further 10% depending on the imposed boundary conditions. Further more depending on the type boundary conditions and geometric thicknesses employed the Y factors (figure 4) can vary at longer crack lengths by as much as a factor of 4. However the present FE calculations correspond well with the available analysis in the literature for the case of the 6mm plate, suggesting that the composite as whole, assuming that no debonding takes place, acts as a rigid body section across the metal epoxy interface.

Sensitivity analysis using a range of Y factors show that the variation in Y translates into fatigue failure life range of a factor of 30 for the steel and the aluminium. Furthermore the fatigue life predictions for both the metal and the epoxy suggest that failure in the bonding which occurs well before the crack growth in metal will reduce the constraint imposed on the structure hence increasing the chance of failure of the metal by fatigue crack growth. For fatigue considerations the defect assessment procedure R6 is applied to determine bounds on tolerable crack sizes for a range

Figure 7 : Number of cycles to Failure for the steel representative material data for a plate thickness of 3mm using a range of Y factors shown in Figure (5).

Figure 8: Comparison of number of cycles to failure between the representative steel, aluminium and epoxy materials using the upper and lower bounds of Y shown in Figure (5)

Figure 9 : R6 diagram for the three geometries using representative Aluminium data.

Figure 10: R6 diagram for the three geometries using representative steel data.

of crack profiles. The R6 analysis suggests that for representative material loads the thin plate is likely to fail by fast fracture whereas the more contained cracks geometries such as the composite plate modelled with an elliptical crack will not.

The role of the adhesive/epoxy is considered, not in terms of its fatigue strength as it is a third order effect compared to the metal, but in terms of its bonding and the subsequent increase in constraint and life extension in the fatigue life of the metal. It is clear that large areas of debonding with reduce the fatigue life of the composite plate since the stresses will not transfer consistently between the metal plates previously bonded together.

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